

Australian
National
University

Crawford School of Public Policy

TTPI

Tax and Transfer Policy Institute

Individualized disability support schemes and their impact on autism diagnoses

TTPI – Policy Brief 1/2026
April 2026

Robert Breunig

Director

Tax and Transfer Policy Institute

Maathumai Ranjan

Tax and Transfer Policy Institute

Tax and Transfer Policy Institute
Crawford School of Public Policy
College of **Asia and the Pacific**

+61 2 6125 9318

tax.policy@anu.edu.au

The Australian National University
Canberra ACT 0200 Australia

www.anu.edu.au

CRICOS Provider No. 00120C

Individualized disability support schemes and their impact on autism diagnoses

Maathumai Ranjan and Robert Breunig

Journal of Health Economics, Volume 105, January 2026, 103100

This note version: April 7, 2026

Key findings

We exploit the staggered geographic rollout of the National Disability Insurance Scheme (NDIS) in Australia to estimate the causal impact of the NDIS on autism diagnoses

- The introduction of the NDIS led to a 32 per cent increase in reported autism prevalence
- The NDIS accounts for 47 per cent of new autism diagnoses since the introduction of the scheme
- Disability service providers have become more likely to provide autism diagnoses and government-subsidised healthcare providers have become less likely to make diagnoses
- The evidence is consistent with the NDIS resulting in a lower threshold for autism diagnoses rather than historical catch-up of under-diagnosed groups

What we knew

- Australia's NDIS, introduced in 2013, represents one of the world's most comprehensive attempts at implementing individualized disability support funding on a national scale. It follows the United Nations Convention on the Rights of People with Disabilities in moving towards providing individual supports rather than a medicalised model for rationed services, United Nations (2006).
- Autism prevalence has been increasingly dramatically around the world with prevalence having doubled in the United States and tripled in Australia between 2010 and 2020; ABS (2022) and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2024).
- The NDIS creates an incentive for autism diagnoses. Widespread anecdotal and media reports have suggested that families seek autism diagnoses in order to access NDIS funding.

What we do

- We use 2011-2021 administrative data drawn from the personal income tax system, the Medicare Consumer Directory and social services data.
- These data are linked to data from the Medicare Benefit Schedules and NDIS administrative data, allowing us to identify the population with autism diagnoses.
- We examine autism diagnoses at the Statistical Area Level 2 (SA2); see ABS (2024).
- We use the staggered rollout of the NDIS to compare 'treated' regions where the NDIS was introduced to 'control' regions where the NDIS is introduced at a later time period.
- We estimate the causal impact of the NDIS on autism diagnoses using the staggered difference-in-differences model of Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021).

Figure 1: Group-time ATT on reported autism prevalence of NDIS rollout

Note: Group year refers to year in which group is first treated. Red markers are pseudo-treatment effects for years where there was no treatment but estimated as if treatment occurred. Blue are group time average treatment effects (ATT).

What we know now

- NDIS introduction in an SA2 causes a large and statistically significant increase in autism diagnoses—see Figure 1.
- Results are robust to allowing for spillover effects, suggesting that greater awareness of autism is not causing these results.
- The increase in diagnoses was very strong among males and stronger in metropolitan areas but fairly evenly distributed across socio-economic background.
- There is no evidence of anticipation of NDIS rollout.
- Consistent with international evidence, rising autism diagnoses are not primarily driven by substitution from intellectual disability or other developmental disorders.
- The NDIS resulted in autism diagnoses for many Australians who would not otherwise have been diagnosed. Additional diagnoses increased from 0.02 per cent in 2013 to 0.77 per cent in 2021—see Figure 2. Since 2013, the impact of the NDIS on reported autism rates accounts for 47 per cent

Figure 2: Increase in autism prevalence from NDIS rollout

What this means for policy

- Individualized, self-directed funding models induce a shift in focus from achieving outcomes to maintaining high levels of financial support. Our research amplifies these concerns.
- Allowing service providers to provide diagnoses creates a conflict of interest with strong financial incentives to provide formal diagnoses.

Where to now?

To ensure the survival of the NDIS, policy-makers should focus on:

- finding ways to deliver disability services in a cost-efficient manner; and
- where possible, providing support and services that allow individuals to achieve independence and well-being without long-term dependence on government support

More information

- Get the full paper at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167629625001353>.
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au

References

ABS (2022). Disability, ageing and carers, australia: Summary of findings, 2022. Australian Bureau of Statistics. <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/health/disability/disability-ageing-and-carers-australia-summary-findings/latest-release>.

ABS (2024). Australian Statistical Geography Standard (ASGS). Australian Bureau of Statistics. <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/statisticalgeography/australian-statistical-geography-standard-asgs>.

Callaway, B. and Sant'Anna, P. H. (2021). Difference-in-differences with multiple time periods, *Journal of Econometrics* **225**(2): 200–230.

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2024). Data and statistics on autism spectrum disorder. www.cdc.gov/autism/data-research/index.html.

The Commonwealth of Australia (2010). Australia's future tax system. Canberra, Australia. Available at <https://treasury.gov.au/review/the-australias-future-tax-system-review/final-report>. Last accessed 14 September 2024.

United Nations (2006). Convention on the rights of persons with disabilities (crpd). <https://www.un.org/development/desa/disabilities/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities.html>.